

State Estimation during Different Accidental Scenarios in a Molten Salt Fast Reactor with Shallow Recurrent Decoders from Out-Core Temperature Measurements

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ABSTRACT

In the landscape of surrogate modelling and Machine Learning techniques for nuclear reactors, Shallow Recurrent Decoders have emerged as a novel architecture able to provide accurate estimation of the (parametric) spatio-temporal state of the system; starting from a few sparse measurements of a simple observable field, such as the temperature, this technique is able to estimate unobservable quantities, thus arising as a reliable tool to monitor the quantities of interest during accidental scenarios in both commercial and innovative reactor designs. This methodology has been proven to be: i) agnostic to sensor positions, ensuring the possibility of inferring the state from out-of-core measurements; ii) robust to noisy data, especially when adopting the ensemble strategy; iii) able to accurately map the non-linear relationship between sensor data and the full state of the system. This work continues to investigate the use of the Shallow Recurrent Decoder architecture to estimate the full-state (neutronic and thermal-hydraulic fields) from out-core temperature measurements in a Molten Salt Fast Reactor under different accidental scenarios, focusing on three types of pump failure scenarios, namely two Unprotected Loss of Fuel Flow (exponential or wavy-exponential decay) and an Overspeed (exponential increase). The most important result from this analysis is that the network, requiring minimal hyperparameter tuning, can discriminate the kind of transient based on the input sensor measurements and hence can produce an accurate state estimation for every field, with a relative error on the test set being below 5%. Thus, this investigation further assesses the capabilities of Shallow Recurrent Decoders as a fundamental brick towards the development of digital twins for new generation reactors.

Keywords: State Estimation, Shallow Recurrent Decoders, Molten Salt Reactor, Reduced Order Modelling, Machine Learning

1. INTRODUCTION

The accurate estimation of the internal state of a nuclear reactor represents a fundamental challenge for ensuring operational safety and is a crucial aspect for the development of accurate digital twins. Innovative nuclear reactor systems, such as the Molten Salt Fast Reactor (MSFR), present several challenges for sensing due to the strong non-linear coupling between different physics (e.g., neutronics and thermal-hydraulics), the use of high-temperature coolants, and the limited availability of in-core instrumentation. Especially for the MSFR, where the fissile material is dissolved in a molten salt, the harsh and hostile environment severely constrains the number and placement of sensors, making traditional

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in-core state estimation techniques impractical [1]. To solve this issue, data-driven and Machine Learning (ML) techniques can be very useful for their strong versatility and flexibility, provided that they can infer the reactor state from sparse sensors: this capability is of primary importance for real-time monitoring, control, and therefore digital twin applications. In addition, these methodologies must be able to obtain the full state reconstruction, starting from partial observations only, since not all the quantities of interest can be directly measured; for instance, it is relatively easy to obtain measurements of the neutron flux or the temperature, but nearly impossible to locally observe the velocity field.

In recent years, the growing availability of high-fidelity multi-physics simulations and the increasing reliability of ML techniques have opened new opportunities for state reconstruction in nuclear systems [2]. The use of appropriate reduction and surrogate methods is necessary in state estimation problems, since the computational time needed to obtain a prediction of the state must be independent of the solution time of the high-fidelity model. Among the various methods, a combination of Reduced Order Modelling (ROM) with neural networks has been widely adopted in fluid dynamics, mechanics, and nuclear reactors [3, 4], allowing for a substantial reduction of the computational costs while retaining the dominant physical features of the system. Within this context, Shallow Recurrent Decoders (SHRED) [5, 6, 7] have emerged as a promising architecture for mapping sparse time-series sensor data to high-dimensional reactor states [8]. These architectures combine a long short-term memory network for temporal feature extraction with a shallow decoder for spatial field reconstruction. SHRED enables accurate state estimation even from a limited number of measures and without the need for extensive hyperparameter tuning. Furthermore, the approach has demonstrated robustness to noise and agnosticism to sensor positions; features that are crucial for actual deployment in nuclear environments [6].

Building upon previous studies by the authors [6, 8] that successfully applied SHRED to a class of accidental transients in molten salt systems for state prediction and parametric reconstruction, the present work extends the methodology to different parametric accidental conditions. The paper focuses on the ability to identify the specific accidental scenario from a few out-of-core temperature measurements and use their temporal information to reconstruct the full multi-physics state in an MSFR, composed of 18 different fields; three classes of accidents related to primary pump malfunction are considered: Unprotected Loss of Fuel Flow (ULOFF), Oscillatory ULOFF (OscillULOFF), and Overspeed.

2. SHALLOW RECURRENT DECODERS

Shallow Recurrent Decoders [5] are a neural network architecture aiming at mapping the trajectories of sparse time-series measures $\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^{L \times s}$ (being L the length of the trajectory and s the number of sensors) to the high-dimensional state $\Psi \in \mathbb{R}^{\mathcal{N}_h}$ of the system, being \mathcal{N}_h the dimension of the state corresponding to the mesh cells or points for a single field. The network architecture includes a recurrent unit, such as a long short-term memory network (LSTM) with sequence length L , designed to learn the temporal dynamics hidden in the measures, followed by a shallow decoder (SDN) aimed at mapping the latent space learnt by the recurrent unit to the high-dimensional state. The original architecture produces, as output, the high-dimensional state, leading to a strong increase in the computational requirements during the network training phase (recall that for typical MP nuclear problems, $\mathcal{N}_h \sim 10^{4-7}$).

To improve the training times, aiming at keeping them as low as possible, a compressed version of SHRED exploiting the Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) has been proposed [6, 7]: instead of learning the mapping of the full state, the network now learns the reduced dynamics spanned by the reduced coefficients $\mathbf{v} \in \mathbb{R}^r$, being the projection of the high-dimensional state through the SVD spatial modes $\mathbf{U} \in \mathbb{R}^{\mathcal{N}_h \times r}$, i.e. $\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{U}^T \Psi$. This compressive strategy strongly reduces the computational costs of the training phase, focusing on estimating the most dominant physics. The spatial SVD modes \mathbf{U} identify the main spatial structures from the training data, encoding the temporal and parametric dependence in the reduced coefficients.

SHRED comes with other important advantages compared to other machine learning methods [5, 6, 7]:

Figure 1. SHRED architecture applied to the Molten Salt Fast Reactor [8]. Three out-of-core sensors are used to measure the temperature T . The sensor time series are used to construct a latent temporal sequence model which is mapped to the compressive representations of all spatio-temporal field variables. The compressive representations can then be mapped to the original state space by the Singular Value Decomposition (SVD).

(i) it is able to work with very few sensors, from 3 to 5; (ii) it is agnostic to sensor positions, provided that the output measurements are statistically significant; (iii) it requires minimal hyper-parameter tuning, in fact the same architecture (with the same number of layers and neurons) has been proved to be sufficiently flexible and able to deal with very different physics (both the LSTM and the SDN network are composed of 2 hidden layers, the ones of the former with 64 neurons each, whereas those of the latter consist of 350 and 400 neurons); (iv) the training can be performed even on a personal computer, without the need of powerful GPUs, and this is especially true when working in compressive mode. The most interesting feature is perhaps the agnosticism to sensor positions: the fundamental justification for this behaviour can be related to the time-delay embedding and the temporal learning capabilities of recurrent networks through the Takens embedding theorem [5, 7].

The SHRED architecture has been implemented in Python using the Pytorch package; the original code [5] has been adapted for the present application, and it is openly available at github.com/ERMETE-Lab/NuSHRED. The notebooks needed to obtain the results of this paper are available as well.

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS

This work investigates the application of SHRED and its reconstruction capabilities of different accidental scenarios in a Molten Salt Fast Reactor, parametrised with respect to the input condition, using a few sparse out-of-core temperature measurements. This section includes a brief description of the multi-physics model used, including the scenarios under consideration, and the main results on the state estimation process will be given.

3.1. Multi-physics Model of the Molten Salt Fast Reactor

The Molten Salt Fast Reactor represents a unique design among new generation reactors, having a Th-based fuel in liquid form acting both as fuel and coolant. As said, this reactor is very useful in assessing the capabilities of ROM-based state estimation methods, due to the strong coupling between fluid dynamics and neutronics and the significant challenges for sensing [1]. The authors have already investigated the possibility of inferring the state of the reactor from out-core sensors, using both classical ROM methods [1] and the SHRED architecture [6, 8], obtaining promising results in both cases. This work extends the methodology to consider different parametric input conditions, assessing the learning capabilities of the SHRED architecture from sparse out-of-core temperature sensors only.

The paper adopts the 2D axisymmetric wedge (5°) of the EVOL geometry of the MSFR, including also an additional external layer of thickness 20 cm to mimic the presence of the Hastelloy reflector [6] in which temperature sensors are placed. The model implements coupled neutronics and thermal-hydraulics, using multi-group diffusion for the former and RANS with Realizable $\kappa - \varepsilon$ turbulence model for the latter, with the Boussinesq approximation to account for buoyancy effects. Furthermore, a momentum source and a heat sink represent the primary loop pump and the heat exchanger, respectively. More details about the multi-physics model, for the interested reader, can be found in [9, 6].

	ULOFF	OscillUOFF	Overspeed
Function Shape $f(\cdot)$	$e^{-t/\tau}$	$e^{-t/5} \cdot [1 + 0.2 \sin(\omega t)]$	$e^{-t/\tau}$
Parameter Range	$\tau \in [1, 10] \text{ s}^{-1}$	$\omega \in [0.5, 5] \text{ s}^{-1}$	$\tau \in [-14, -7]$
Number of Samples	21	25	8

Table I. Characterisation of the different accidental scenarios investigated, focusing on the parametric input function $f(t; \mu)$, showing the shape of the function, the range of the adopted parameters and the number of samples.

Table I reports a summary of the shapes for the momentum function $f(\cdot)$, the range of the parameter used for the three different transients, and the number of samples collected (corresponding to the number of parametric simulations performed for each transient), being $N_s = 54$ in total. Each transient has a time interval $\mathcal{T} = [0, 30] \text{ s}$, with a $\Delta t_{\text{saving}} = 0.05 \text{ s}$, thus saving $N_t = 600$ temporal snapshots for each parametric trajectory. The dataset is composed by 18 coupled fields, describing the neutron economy and the thermal-hydraulics of the system: in particular, for this case, six group fluxes in energy $\{\phi_g\}_{g=1}^6$, eight groups of delayed neutrons $\{c_k\}_{k=1}^8$ and the power density q are considered for the neutronic side, to which the thermal-hydraulics fields, namely pressure, temperature, velocity ($p_{rgh} \equiv \tilde{p}, T, \mathbf{u}$), must be added. Except for the velocity \mathbf{u} , all the others are scalar fields; the number of spatial degrees of freedom is $\mathcal{N}_h = 94611$ for the scalar fields and $\mathcal{N}_h = 283833$ for the velocity. Overall, the full-order state space vector is $\mathcal{V} = [\phi_1, \dots, \phi_6, c_1, \dots, c_8, p, T, \mathbf{u}]$. The data splitting is performed randomly with respect to the 54 parameters as follows: train 66%, valid 13%, test 21%.

As part of the data pre-processing, the training snapshots for each field are used to generate a set of fundamental basis functions obtained through the SVD. This compression technique can be considered as the foundation of any reduced model due to its intrinsic capability of separating the spatial behaviour from the time and parametric one, through a linear combination of a limited number of spatial modes $\mathbf{U} \in \mathbb{R}^{\mathcal{N}_h \times r}$ as follows: $\mathbf{\Psi} \simeq \mathbf{U}\mathbf{v}$. In particular, this approach becomes useful because the SVD rank r is generally much lower than the spatial degrees of freedom \mathcal{N}_h of the high-fidelity dataset: in this work, it has been chosen to select $r = 10$ for every field, by looking at the decay of the singular values (not reported for the sake of brevity, available on the companion GitHub repository). Accordingly, the output size of the decoder is 180 (without the compression stage the high-dimensional state would have $\sim 1.9 \cdot 10^6$ degrees of freedom).

Regarding the sensors and their positions, SHRED is agnostic to sensor positions, as shown in previous

Figure 2. Mean relative errors ε_1^r (including standard deviation) for every field for each reduced coefficient, with respect to the test set: the lowest errors are always associated with the first order coefficients.

Figure 3. Mean relative errors ε_2^ψ for every field (including standard deviation), with respect to the test set: the observable field is T (first one) and the error associated is generally the lowest, whereas the most difficult field to reconstruct is the velocity.

works [5, 6, 7, 8]. However, within the nuclear reactor community, several algorithms based on the Empirical Interpolation Method (EIM) [10] have been proposed to select the optimal positions of sensors in order to maximise the information extracted from the physical system. Therefore, this work uses the Discrete EIM method to select the first 20 candidate positions in the out-core reflector region for SHRED; then, 10 configurations are extracted by randomly picking 3 out of the 20 possible positions, thus allowing SHRED to work in ensemble mode, making it more robust against noise and allowing the estimation of a confidence interval for the reconstruction. The number of configurations has been selected following previous studies made in [6, 8].

3.2. State Estimation with SHRED

Once the data have been generated, the SVD has been performed and the reduced coefficients have been obtained for every field, the measurements of the temperature at the selected sensor positions are extracted from the full-order snapshots, with sensors assumed to be point-wise. An ensemble of 10 different SHRED models is trained, each one associated with a different configuration of sensors. The training of each SHRED model takes about 4.3 minutes on a MacBook Pro M4 (2024).

Once the models have been trained, it is important to assess their accuracy with respect to unseen data (the test set). Two different metrics have been defined for the reduced coefficients v_r (ε_1^r) and for the high-dimensional fields Ψ (ε_2^ψ), where $N_s^{test} = 11$ and $N_t = 600$:

Figure 4. Temporal evolution of the average values of selected fields (T, ϕ_1, c_1) for some of the test conditions, normalised with respect to the initial condition.

Figure 5. Contour plots at the last time step for a test parameter (OscillULOFF transient, the most complex one) of temperature T (a), velocity \mathbf{u} (b), fast flux ϕ_1 (c) and first precursors group c_1 (d). From left to right: full-order solution, mean of the SHRED models, the associated standard deviation and the residual field. The prediction with SHRED provides a correct local state estimation of both the observable and the unobservable quantities.

$$\varepsilon_1^r = \frac{1}{\langle v_r \rangle} \cdot \frac{1}{N_s^{\text{test}}} \sum_{n=1}^{N_s^{\text{test}}} \left(\frac{1}{N_t} \sum_{j=1}^{N_t} |v_r^{n,j} - \hat{v}_r^{n,j}| \right) \quad \text{and} \quad \varepsilon_2^\psi = \frac{1}{N_s^{\text{test}}} \sum_{n=1}^{N_s^{\text{test}}} \left(\frac{1}{N_t} \sum_{j=1}^{N_t} \frac{\|\Psi_j^{\mu n} - \hat{\Psi}_j^{\mu n}\|_2}{\|\Psi_j^{\mu n}\|_2} \right) \quad (1)$$

These two metrics represent a mean relative error for each reduced coefficient/output of the SHRED architecture and the reconstructed high-dimensional field (obtained by decoding using the SVD modes). Figure 2 reports the metric ε_1^r for each reduced coefficient v_ψ^j for the generic field ψ at rank $j \in [1, r]$. SHRED is more inclined to reconstruct better the lowest coefficients, which contain the most dominant temporal features of the dataset (as the coefficients are sorted according to their relative importance with respect to the overall dynamics of the starting dataset); conversely, SHRED tends to have more difficulties for high-order modes, which contains smaller scales structures; regardless, for all coefficients the error is always below 5%.

Regarding the high-dimensional fields, Figure 3 shows the metric ε_2^ψ for the generic field ψ , including the standard deviation of the error. The observable field is the temperature T (highlighted): being the observable field, its error is the lowest. Each unobservable field has an error below 2%, apart from the velocity field: this result is expected, as the velocity field is usually the most difficult field to reconstruct (being a vectorial field with small-scale features). The neutron fluxes and the power density share most of the spatial features, thus the error is comparable.

Focusing on the reconstruction of the high-dimensional fields for unknown accidental scenarios, Figure 4 shows the dynamics of the average values of some fields of interest ($T, q, \phi_1, c_1, c_5, c_8$), comparing the true solution, the mean prediction from SHRED and the associated confidence interval (as a result of the ensemble procedure [6]). There is a very good agreement, as the SHRED prediction is very close to the true solution, showing the capabilities of SHRED to correctly identify the accidental scenario and the associated input condition starting from the sparse temperature measurement only, and later produce an accurate output able to follow the dynamical evolution of the (averaged) quantities of interest.

In the end, Figure 5 shows the contour plots of the true solution (FOM), the mean SHRED prediction, its standard deviation, and the associated residual, for the temperature (observed field), the velocity, the fast flux, and the first group of precursors, considering a test set trajectory of the OscillULOFF scenario ($\omega^* = 2.75$ rad/s) and the last time step. For every field, there is a good agreement between SHRED and the ground-truth, with the most significant discrepancies being quite localised. The standard deviation provides some information regarding the missing physics cut by the SVD truncation, for instance some smaller scales effects near the recirculation region.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This paper has investigated the possibility of adopting Shallow Recurrent Decoders as a data-driven reduced model able to estimate the full state in a Molten Salt Reactor (including both neutronics and thermal-hydraulic fields), under different parametric accidental scenarios related to the primary pump failure. The reduced model requires few sparse temperature measurements, collected only in the Hastelloy reflector, and it is able to discriminate from the time-series data of the measures the kind of transient and reconstruct the state of the system. In fact, it is possible to obtain accurate predictions of the full state of the reactor, with a relative error below 2% (except for the velocity field, which is around 4%), with a quite shallow neural network, with fewer than 1000 parameters, which can be trained even on a personal computer, and featuring minimal hyperparameter tuning. In the end, this methodology is mature enough to be considered as the reference for state estimation for nuclear reactors, to be integrated in the monitoring pipeline of digital twins.

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